

Exploring the Intersection of Microbial Science and Sustainable Development: Opportunities for Education and Innovation

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Abstract

In 2015, the United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, anchored on 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that address global environmental, economic, and social challenges. This study explores the underutilized potential of microbial science in advancing the SDGs, with a specific focus on how microorganisms can contribute to sustainability through applications in energy, agriculture, waste management, and public health. Despite this potential, the integration of microbial innovations into sustainability frameworks remains limited due to widespread microbial illiteracy. This paper argues that increasing public and policy-level awareness of microorganisms as agents of sustainable development can drive innovation and accelerate progress toward the SDGs. It concludes that microbial literacy is a foundational enabler of sustainable innovation. Accordingly, it recommends the inclusion of microbial science in sustainability education curricula, greater investment in microbial research, and interdisciplinary collaborations to promote microbe-based solutions for a sustainable future.

Keywords: Microbial science, microorganisms, sustainability, SDGs, innovation

Introduction

In 2015, the United Nations adopted the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which were fronted as a blueprint for the achievement of a better and more sustainable future for the planet. The SDGs address various global challenges facing humanity, including hunger, poverty, sustainability problems in cities and communities, slow economic growth, innovation and industrialization, disparities in access to quality education and healthcare, clean water, and energy, and climate change (Mishra *et al.*, 2023). Current practices with regard to these challenges raise the overarching problem of sustainability. For instance, efforts to boost economic growth through increased industrialization are a major cause of extensive environmental degradation (Bajja *et al.*, 2024). Industrialization is typically associated with increased emissions of methane, carbon dioxide, nitrous oxide, and other greenhouse gases in addition to rapid urbanization, a double-ended outcome that can either promote sustainable development or increase pollution (Bajja *et al.*, 2024). Industrialization, together with its highlighted potential consequences, relates to most of the other SDGs, demonstrating a correlation among the SDGs. This relationship has been studied extensively, with results confirming that the SDGs interact with and influence each other (Pakkan *et al.*, 2022). As such, achieving all 17 SDGs requires overarching solutions that recognize their interrelation and address each goal relative to its interaction with other SDGs. To this end, the intersection of microbial science and sustainable development provides multiple opportunities for education and innovation geared toward the achievement of the SDGs.

Microbial science, or microbiology, is the study of microscopic organisms, including bacteria, fungi, viruses, molds, and algae. Microorganisms are versatile and metabolically versatile, allowing for their application in various industries and fields for purposes that promote sustainability (Qumsani, 2024). For instance, microorganisms such as bacteria can aid in the achievement of SDG 7, which hopes to achieve universal access to clean and affordable energy, through the production of clean energy from biomass (Akinsemolu, 2023). In their use in the production of energy, microorganisms use waste, linking SDG 7 to SDG 13, which focuses on climate action and champions environmental conservation (Fagunwa & Olabiwoninu, 2020).

Similarly, microorganisms can remediate wasteland and wastewater, which would advance the sustainability of the industrial processes that produce the waste while removing toxins and contaminants from water to cleanse it and make it safe for drinking and agriculture (Akinsemolu, 2023). This single application links SDG 9, which focuses on innovation and industrialization, to SDG 6, which is concerned with the universal availability of clean drinking water, SDG 13, which is concerned with addressing the effects of climate change, including water pollution, and SDG 12, which is concerned with the responsible consumption of resources such as clean water (Fagunwa & Olanbiwoninu, 2020). Evidently, microbial science yields multiple applications of microorganisms that can be employed and adapted to contribute to the current efforts toward sustainability. However, microbiology can hinder efforts to attain sustainability in as many ways as it can boost them. In fact, microorganisms attract a negative connotation due to their association with diseases, a perception that is linked to the lack of scientific literacy in microbiology (Karayanni *et al.*, 2024). This presents an opportunity for education with the aim of raising awareness of the link between microbial science and sustainability and promoting innovation.

Harnessing the applications of microbial science in pursuit of sustainability requires the exploration of the points of convergence of the two concepts. To this end, we review the existing knowledge on the applications of microbiology in the achievement of sustainability and use it to infer opportunities for education on the intersection of the two concepts and innovation in the use of microorganisms to promote sustainable development.

Methodology

This study uses literature on microbiology and sustainability to explore the intersection of microbial science and sustainable development and identify opportunities for innovation and education to improve the role of microbiology in the achievement of the SDGs. To this end, the researcher used Google Scholar, Scopus, Sage, and Elsevier to identify relevant literature on the topic of study. The keywords Microbial Science, Microbiology, Sustainable Development Goals,

Sustainability, Sustainable Development, Innovation, and Education were used to identify studies between 2010-2023. This period was selected to ensure that all information used is up-to-date and the study reflects the current status of research and literature on the topic of study. After the identification

of potential studies, a rigorous screening process was employed to assess the relevance, accuracy, and quality of the sources. Finally, information was extracted from the selected sources.

The Role of Microorganisms in Sustainable Development

Innovation in microbial science has led to the widespread use of microorganisms across various industries, in environmental conservation, in the maintenance of plant and animal health, and in the sustenance of the global food chain. These applications of microorganisms, and their role in building a sustainable world, have been studied extensively and linked to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals as seen in Figure 1 below. The American Society for Microbiology (ASM) recognizes the critical role of microbial science in sustainable development. In a panel hosted by the society in 2021, ASM panelists explored various applications of microbes and linked them to sustainable development by highlighting their contributions to specific SDGs. Highlights include the role of microorganisms in the protection and fertilization of the soil, which promotes the reduction of world hunger, and the use of microorganisms in the manufacture of drugs and medication, which promotes the achievement of SDG 3, which is concerned with the promotion of health and wellbeing, and the use of microorganisms in the bioremediation of wastewater, promoting the achievement of SDG 6, which is concerned with ensuring universal access to clean water (Robbins, 2021). Similar general evaluations of microbes and their role in the achievement of specific SDGs identify uses of the microorganisms that relate to specific SDGs. Notably, Akinsemolu (2018) explores this link between microbial science and sustainable production by outlining various applications of microorganisms alongside the corresponding SDG. Highlights include the use of microorganisms in the production, preservation, and fortification of food with nutrients, which promotes the achievement of SDG 2 on the elimination of hunger, and SDG 3, which targets the promotion of universal health and well-being and the use of microorganisms to produce organic fertilizers, aiding in the achievement of SDG 13 on climate action, SDG 15 through the protection of life on land from toxic fertilizers, and SDG 10 through the reduction of inequality through sustainable agricultural processes (Akinsemolu, 2018). While some studies and literature highlight general applications of microorganisms in sustainable development, others single out specific SDGs and delve deep into the mechanisms or microorganisms that make them suitable for specific applications in pursuit of sustainable development as follows.

Figure 1: The Role of Microorganisms in Sustainable Development (Source: Author)

Poverty and Hunger

SDGs 1 and 2 are concerned with eradicating poverty and hunger to achieve sustainable development. The link between poverty, hunger, and sustainable development is well-established. Hunger and poverty are the products of war and conflict, poor governance, climate change, inequality, and poor agricultural practices and output (Atukunda *et al.*, 2021). Garcia, Perez, and Sanz (2018) link the two to sustainability by identifying a causal relationship between hunger and poverty in their finding that hunger and associated challenges such as malnutrition and food insecurity are deeply rooted in poverty (Garcia, Perez & Sanz, 2018). From a sustainable solution standpoint, hunger and poverty are environmental problems, whose solutions lie in innovative solutions to improve food systems and agriculture, strengthened by education, research, and social sustainability training (Atukunda *et al.*, 2021). Several studies explore the innovative applications of microorganisms in improving food and agricultural production to address food insecurity, which has been proven to contribute significantly to the eradication of poverty (Modi, 2018). Therefore, the food applications of microbes have been explored extensively in literature and research. Kaur, Al-Tawaha, and Karnwal (2023) explore the beneficial impact of microorganisms in the production of food, which is linked to the health of the population and sustainability. They explore applications such as the use of bacteria and fungi in the preparation, and processing of various types of food, in the extension of the shelf life of some foods to reduce wastage and guarantee food safety, and in the production of biodegradable food packaging that

ensure food safety in transit and storage. Ciani et al. (2021) add a dimension of sustainability to the application of microbes in food production by highlighting their role in addressing externalities such as water and soil contamination, biodiversity loss, and soil erosion, which impair the efficiency of food production systems. They suggest addressing these inefficiencies through the use of microbial biomass derived from algae, bacteria, yeast, or fungi as a nutritious source of food for animals reared for meat and milk, which promotes sustainable development by increasing food production while reducing the adverse impacts of agriculture on the environment (Ciani *et al.*, 2021). In addition to the use of microbes to produce highly nutritious animal feeds using fewer resources relative to the conventional production of animal feeds, microorganisms are natural fixators of nitrogen in the soil, which together with their active role in the biodegradation of organic matter, degradation of heavy metals and pollutants, and the binding water to the soil, promotes food growth, improving agricultural production (Noor-Hassim *et al.*, 2023). Evidently, microorganisms are valuable resources in the sustainable production of food (Malkawi & Kapiel, 2024). Their role in the efficiency of the food production system, the fortification of food with nutrients, ability to increase food production using limited resources contribute to sustainable development by promoting food security, which addresses hunger and malnutrition, and increased food production amidst reduced costs of producing food, advancing the achievement of SDG 1 on poverty eradication and SDG 2, which is concerned with eliminating hunger.

Health and Wellbeing

Public opinion on microorganisms is ridden with misconceptions, principally the association of the terms bacteria, virus, and microorganisms with diseases (Kokkinias *et al.*, 2024). In fact, between 15% and 20% of citizens reported fearing microorganisms, while 45.5% of the population concedes that microorganisms are underrepresented and understudied in school (Spernjak, Puhmeister & Sorgo, 2021). This negative perception of microorganisms stems from limited education on their applications, presenting an opportunity for increased education to increase microbiology literacy, which will foster innovation on further applications of microorganisms (Fidiastuti *et al.*, 2024). One promising area, which increased microbiology literacy can improve, is the development of novel applications of microorganisms in healthcare. The crucial role of microorganisms in the achievement of SDG 3, which centers on health and well-being, has been studied and represented extensively in existing literature both through general overviews of the applications of microorganisms in healthcare and specific studies

that explore the application of specific genera of microorganisms in the healthcare industry. Marco (2021) provides a general overview of the benefits of microorganisms to human health, highlighting current and potential ways of adapting some microbial compounds and activities to yield positive benefits such as the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases, cardiovascular diseases, metabolic diseases and cancer, and the promotion of gut, skin, respiratory, reproductive, and oral health. Whereas general studies do not delve into the specific microbial activities that yield health benefits, Abbas et al. (2021) highlight different microorganisms alongside their specific applications in the healthcare industry, noting the affordability and sustainability of the use of microorganisms in the production of pharmaceuticals and dietary supplements. They recognize the role of bacteria in the production of dietary supplements such as probiotics and antibiotics that activate the immune system to fight harmful bacteria. Notably, innovation is a central theme in studies that highlight the applications of microbial science in promoting health and well-being. Genetic engineering is fronted as an innovative way of enhancing microbes to combat pathogens (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). The contribution of microbial science to health and well-being is not limited to the applications of microorganisms in the pharmaceutical industry. Microbial metabolism has the potential to remove harmful and toxic pollutants from water (Gur, Bakhshpour & Denizli, 2021).

While the study does not link the use of microbes in the bioremediation of water to healthcare or sustainable development, it inspires the inference that the removal of contaminants and pollutants from water promotes access to clean drinking water, which aligns with SDG 6, which is concerned with universal access to clean water. More recent studies have explored innovation in the use of microbial science to break down contaminants and toxins in water into harmless or less harmful compounds (Sharma *et al.*, 2022).

Quality Education

SDG 4 focuses on ensuring access to inclusive and equitable education in the pursuit of promoting lifelong learning opportunities universally. Literature on education relative to microbiology focuses primarily on recognizing the need for the popularization of microbial science, with education as the primary tool for the achievement of this objective. Fraga (2018) acknowledges the widespread misconceptions about microorganisms and proposes teaching approaches that provide students with a comprehensive understanding of microbes and their role in nature as a way of reinforcing their

importance. It's important that the need for the dissemination of this knowledge extends to the public to address the persistent association of microbes and diseases. Whereas Fraga (2018) highlights the importance of microbial science education, other studies and literature create a roadmap for the application of various approaches to ensure quality education in microbial science. Fahnert (2016) cites the rising food insecurity, increasing prevalence of infectious diseases, and growing antibiotic resistance as some of the reasons for the need to engage younger generations in microbiology and proposes technology-enhanced education as an appropriate teaching approach. The gamification of microbial science is fronted as one way of getting learners more involved and focused on microbial science (Estoppey *et al.*, 2024). The overarching objective of all efforts to promote education on microbial science is the achievement of universal microbiology literacy. To this end, Timmis (2023) suggests the universal adoption of a teaching approach that emphasizes the relevance of microorganisms, their impact on sustainability, and personal and societal responsibility in furthering microbiology literacy. While the literature on approaches to promote quality and lifelong learning on microorganisms and their applications is adequate, an evaluation of the link between microbiology education or literacy and innovation is missing, presenting a gap for further research. However, the universal relationship between education and innovation is well-studied and documented, establishing a cycle of innovation as a fundamental pillar of the knowledge economy and education as a proven way of fostering innovation (Biasi, Deming & Moser, 2021). Research to establish the link between microbiology education and literacy and innovation in the field can build on the cycle of education and innovation to uncover new integrations between the two and capitalize on quality education to unlock innovations in microbial science that promote sustainable development.

Clean and Affordable Energy

SDG 7 is concerned with ensuring universal access to reliable, affordable, modern, and sustainable energy. The role of energy as one of the crucial elements of sustainability has been studied extensively in different dimensions, highlighting the world's reliance on energy for survival stemming from its applications in household and commercial heating and lighting, the reliance of integral household and industrial appliances on energy, applications in the propulsion of all means of transportation, industrial applications in the production of consumer and commercial products, and other uses. This integral role of energy as a driver of most human activities is featured extensively in the literature on sustainability.

Turkogly & Kardogan (2018) explain the link between energy and sustainable efficiency by demonstrating the role of energy in the economic development of a nation, entertaining the inference that countries, particularly the developing countries that make up the Global South, can only sustain economic development if they produce or have access to efficient energy. However, this approach to discussing the link between energy efficiency and sustainable development does not adequately address the impediments that various countries face in efforts to generate or access clean and efficient energy. For instance, the resources needed to transform raw sources of energy, such as the technical and technological capacity to generate energy, are a major hindrance to the production of sustainable energy (Vezzoli *et al.*, 2018). Further, the current global energy system is primarily based on fossil fuels, which hinders universal access to energy by limiting access to countries with adequate resources. With access to energy and the nature of energy used being directly linked to the quality of life, the need for sustainable sources of energy is imperative. To this end, Chen *et al.* (2022) question the extent to which renewable energy contributes to the achievement of the SDGs. To answer the question, they identify different types of energy that contribute to sustainable development through their renewability, low cost of production, and low environmental impact. Principal among these sources of energy is biomass power, which is produced using the metabolic and enzymatic activities of microorganisms (Wang *et al.*, 2021). The use of microorganisms as a source of energy is not a novel idea. Different microbial technologies for the production of energy have been tested, and some adopted commercially. Fuels produced using microorganisms are biodegradable and often produced from biomass, translating to low-cost, renewable, and environmentally friendly energy. This application of microorganisms has attracted investment and research, sparking innovation as evident in the advanced technologies that have been developed to accelerate the production of biofuels (Sahni, Singh & Baweja, 2021). While the link between clean energy and sustainable production has been established, there is a gap in studies and literature linking the two and microbial science education or microbial literacy.

Economic Growth and Innovation

Hirai (2022) calls for the need to establish a balance between economic growth and sustainable development, suggesting that sometimes, the objectives of economic growth and environmental goals do not align. This conflict between economic development and environmental conservation stems from the reliance of current economic growth models on the overexploitation of natural resources, the

adoption of cost-reducing or production methods that destroy the environment, and unsustainable consumption that puts pressure on resources drawn from the environment. Eventually, these approaches to economic growth have the opposite effect on the environment since as Lampert (2019) confirms, the unsustainable exploitation of resources precedes an inevitable decline in economic growth. This reversal or slowing down of economic growth alongside environmental degradation has been studied in China, whose excessive exploitation of natural resources has caused significant ecological damage and slowed down efforts to achieve SDG 8, which is concerned with promoting sustainable economic growth (Xu *et al.*, 2023). A sociological approach to the conflicting goals of sustainable development and economic development confirmed the observations in China with a bold statement that while the SDGs purport to promote environmental sustainability, they favor economic growth over the sustainable use of resources, effectively hindering the attainment of sustainable development (Eisenmenger *et al.*, 2020). Microbial science presents multiple innovative solutions that have the potential to balance economic growth and sustainable development. Over the past decade, some of these solutions have been studied extensively, bringing out the role of innovation as the bridge between economic development and sustainability. For instance, Graham and Ledesma-Amaro (2023) reference a microbial food revolution characterized by the use of microbial biomass as animal food and some microorganisms as human food. Various microorganisms, which are good sources of protein and vitamins, have been adapted as human food while microbial biomass, which is low-cost and cheaper to produce, more environmentally friendly to produce, and not susceptible to the effects of climate change, guaranteeing constant supply while promoting environmental sustainability (Linder, 2019). The use of microorganisms in the production of clean energy further drives sustainable development through the production of renewable and affordable energy, whose generation causes relatively less environmental damage. Innovation has driven the application of microorganisms in production processes in other industries, replacing unsustainable materials, unsustainable production processes, and unsustainable sources of energy in various industries, including the pharmaceuticals, cosmetic, food, and laundry products industries (Salama *et al.*, 2022).

Climate Action

The natural environment is the primary source of the resources used in the production of consumer and commercial products, the construction of homes, commercial buildings, and infrastructure, the

production of food, water, and other products needed to sustain life on the planet. The excessive nature of the current level of exploitation of these resources and its negative environmental impact have been studied widely and are well-established, as is the need for their sustainable exploitation. Notably, different dimensions of the environment and its link to sustainable development have been explored. For instance, companies and commercial enterprises that adopt environmentally responsible behavior such as energy efficiency and carbon-emission reduction were found to have a positive impact on sustainable development (Wu, Qing & Jin, 2022). Evidently, corporate and industry activities that target the achievement of SDG 13, which focuses on climate action, drive the concerned industries towards sustainability by limiting their negative effects on the environment. Various studies front microbial science as a solution to the excessive exploitation of natural resources through the role of microorganisms as cheaper and renewable raw materials for various industries. A second dimension of climate action and sustainability relates to approaches to the treatment of waste. Waste from households and emissions from industrial activities are major causes of environmental degradation, hindering efforts to achieve sustainable development by impairing the ability of land and water to produce natural resources and support agriculture, hindering efforts to achieve sustainability in cities and communities, affecting population health negatively, and causing overall environmental degradation. This hinders efforts to achieve SDGs 1, 2, 3, 6, 11, 13, 14, and 15, which are concerned with eradicating poverty and hunger, promoting good health, securing universal access to clean water and sanitation, building sustainable cities and communities, protecting the environment, and protecting life below water and on land (Pedersen, 2018). Innovations in microbial science promise to advance positive climate action by reducing reliance on natural resources as raw materials in industrial processes and sustainable ways of treating waste in water and on land. To this end, various microorganisms with the potential of breaking down toxins and contaminants in wastewater and soil have been studied (Atuchin *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2022). From these studies, the inference that microorganisms restore soil and water quality, promoting sustainability, is evident. Ultimately, the synergistic effects of the treatment of wastewater and contaminated soil using microorganisms have been studied, and their contributions to sustainable development established (Gusheva *et al.*, 2022).

Discussion

There is a widespread misconception of microbes as causes of diseases and limited knowledge of the purpose, abilities, and potential applications of microorganisms. As various studies have proven, education is positively linked to innovation in any field. Therefore, the limited knowledge of the potential of microbial science is hindering innovation in the field. The adoption of mass educational efforts to enhance microbial literacy is bound to increase innovation in the adaption of microorganisms for different applications in pursuit of sustainable development. A unique opportunity for education is the integration of traditional knowledge and uses of microorganisms, such as their use in food production processes, waste treatment, or in the preparation of medicine, with modern technologies. Second, the versatility of microorganisms presents multiple opportunities for their linked adaptation to various processes in pursuit of sustainable development. Currently, the application of microbial science in environmental conservation through the remediation of wastewater and contaminated soil has been studied widely and its potential established. Future research can explore ways of enhancing the output of microbial biomass and some microorganisms as potential alternatives to resource-intensive agricultural output, providing cost-effective, nutritious, and easy-to-produce food that does not stress the environment and requires less land, water, and other natural resources. Third, microorganisms can enrich natural resources such as the soil with nutrients that support the growth of trees and vegetation, which address climate change, supporting efforts to promote environmental sustainability. Innovation efforts could focus on enhancing the ability of these microbes to perform these functions effectively. Ultimately, opportunities for innovation, and further research, include the genetic engineering of microorganisms to enhance their capacity for current applications, adapt them for new applications, and improve their ability to survive in different environments.

Conclusion

Microbial science holds solutions to various global environmental, economic, biological, and social problems, including environmental degradation, sustainable production and consumption, population health, agriculture, and food insecurity. To harness these solutions, focus and research in the intersection of microbial science and sustainable development should focus on education and innovation. For education to successfully play its role as a precursor to innovation in microbiology, it must begin by eliminating the widely held misconceptions about microorganisms before raising

awareness of their existing applications to spark interest in the discovery of potential novel applications or ways of enhancing microbes for better outcomes in current applications. Such innovation will, in turn, broaden the scope of education, creating a mutually beneficial cycle of education and innovation in microbiology.

Recommendations

To fully realize the potential of microbial science in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals, the following actions are recommended:

1. Integrate microbial science into sustainability curricula at all educational levels to build foundational knowledge and correct widespread misconceptions about microorganisms.
2. Invest in interdisciplinary research that bridges microbiology, environmental science, and innovation studies to explore and scale microbial solutions for global sustainability challenges.
3. Promote public awareness campaigns to highlight the beneficial roles of microbes in areas such as waste management, food security, renewable energy, and health.
4. Support innovation hubs and incubators focused on microbial technologies to accelerate the development and commercialization of sustainable microbial applications.
5. Encourage policy frameworks that recognize and support microbial literacy as a component of environmental and scientific education policy.

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Conflict of Interest

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